

Preparation of Optically Active Unsymmetrical Ketones from (+)-Acid Halide

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Optically active unsymmetrical aliphatic ketones (R=alkyl) of the type $R.CO.CH_2.CH_2.CH(CH_3).CH_2.CH_2.COCl$ ($CH_2.CH_2$ where R=Me, Et, Prⁿ, Prⁱ, Buⁿ, Buⁱ, n-amyl, isoamyl) have been prepared¹⁻³ in good yields by the Grignard reaction using anhydrous $CdCl_2$ and (+)- α -(2-methylbutyl)acetyl chloride. Optically active unsymmetrical aromatic ketones of the type $A.CO.CH_2.CH_2.CH(CH_3).CH_2.CH_2.COCl$ have also been prepared in good yields by the Friedel-Crafts reaction using anhydrous $AlCl_3$ and (+)-acid halide. The optical rotations of these ketones have been measured.

By the interosylation of (+)-acid halide and (+)- $CH_2.CH_2.CH_2.CH(CH_3).CH_2.CH_2.COCl$ ($[\alpha]_D^{25} +4.889$, $l=1$) with the Grignard complexes, prepared from different aliphatic alkyl halides R, X (where R=Me, Et, n-Pr, i-Pr, n-Bu, i-Bu, n-amyl, and i-amyl) in presence of anhydrous cadmium chloride, optically active unsymmetrical ketones have been obtained. Also the (+)-acid halide provided optically active unsymmetrical aromatic ketones by the Friedel-Crafts reaction, using anhydrous aluminium chloride. The optical rotations of these unsymmetrical ketones are recorded in Tables I and II.

EXPERIMENTAL

(+)- α -(2-Methylbutyl)acetic Acid.—A solution of KOH (200 g. in 200 ml water; 3.6 M) and (+)- α -methylbutylmalonic ester (1 M, 230 g., d_4^{20} 1.1275; n_D^{20} 1.422; $[\alpha]_D^{25} +4.187$), prepared from (+)-1-bromo-2-(methylbutane) ($[\alpha]_D^{25} +1.074$; 102 g.) and malonic ester (117 g.) in presence of sodium ethoxide (10.6 g. Na and 350 ml anhydrous ethanol) was refluxed for 1 hr on a water bath with occasional shaking. It was then acidified with H_2SO_4 (conc., 174 ml in 450 ml water) and cooled. The contents were refluxed for 3-4 hr. at 120-30° when the two layers separated. The upper layer was extracted with ether, the extracts were washed with water, and dried ($MgSO_4$); on evaporation of the ether, the residual oil separating distilled at 165-68°/26-27 mm, yield 85 g. (85.3%), d_4^{25} 1.0637, n_D^{25} 1.417, $[\alpha]_D^{25} +4.494$. Hailbron reports b.p. 221°, n_D^{20} 1.4211; $[\alpha]_D^{15}$ 7.6 in MeOH; d_4^{20} 0.9149

(+)- α -(2-Methylbutyl)acetyl Chlorides.—To thionyl chloride (37.5 g.) the preceding acid (32.5 g.) was added during 40 min. The excess of thionyl chloride was distilled and

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2. Gilman and Nelson, *Rec. trav. chim.*, 1936, 55, 516.
3. Gilman "Organic Chemistry", Vol. 1, pp. 489-580.
4. Cason, *Chem. Rev.*, 1947, 46, 16.
5. *Idem*, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1948, 69, 2078.

the product collected at 167-74°, yield 57%, d_4^{20} 0.9677, $[\alpha]_D^{25} +4.889$ (1,1). (Found: Cl, 23.12. $C_7H_{13}OCl$ requires Cl, 23.90%). Bailestein quotes for the inactive acid halide as b.p. 167-68°/767 mm; d_4^{20} 0.9677.

General Method for the Preparation of Optically Active Ketones

(a). *Alkyl Ketones*.—To the ice-cooled solution of the Grignard reagent, prepared from alkyl halide (0.2M) and magnesium (0.2M) in ether (100 ml) was added during 5 min. anhydrous cadmium chloride (1.08M, 19.6 g.) and the contents were refluxed for 20 min. The ether was distilled and to the residue was added dry benzene (65 ml); the mixture was distilled and further refluxed when more of benzene (120 ml) was added until a homogeneous solution resulted. To this was added (+)-2-methylbutylacetyl chloride (0.16M, 23.6 g.) rapidly with control of the exothermic reaction. The contents were then stirred vigorously for 10-15 min. and then decomposed with ice and H_2SO_4 (10-15%). The aqueous layer was extracted with benzene and washed with sodium carbonate solution (5%), water, and brine and filtered through a layer of Na_2SO_4 . On evaporation of the solvent, the residue under reduced pressure provided the ketones as recorded in Table I.

TABLE I

Alkyl from.	Density.	B.P. (15-20mm).	Yield.	Ref. index.	$[\alpha]_D^{25}$ ($l=1$).	Formula.	Found.	Reqd.
MeI	0.8390	91-93°	72%	1.4090	4.098	$C_8H_{16}O$	C: 74.82% H: 12.12	75.01% 12.50
EtI	0.9806	102-103°	70	1.4132	4.307	$C_9H_{18}O$	C: 76.00 H: 12.62	76.05 12.66
n-Pr Br	1.0030	130-41°	68	1.4100	2.713	$C_{10}H_{20}O$	C: 76.43 H: 12.52	76.93 12.82
i-Pr Br	1.0060	142-43°	73	1.4100	3.147	$C_{10}H_{20}O$	C: 76.33 H: 12.60	76.93 12.82
n-Bu Br	0.9810	137-39°	68	1.4180	5.826	$C_{11}H_{22}O$	C: 77.45 H: 12.69	77.60 12.94
i-BuBr	0.9883	132-34°	68	1.4151	5.507	$C_{11}H_{22}O$	C: 77.40 H: 11.75	77.66 12.04
n-Amyl Br	0.9824	170-71°	69	1.4250	4.183	$C_{12}H_{24}O$	C: 77.82 H: 12.86	78.27 13.04
i-Amyl Br	0.9837	157-50°	69	1.4210	7.109	$C_{12}H_{24}O$	C: 77.69 H: 12.82	78.27 13.04

(b). *Aryl Ketones*.—The reaction was carried out as usual by the interaction of (+)- α -2-methylbutylacetyl chloride (0.34M, 50.3 g.) and aromatic compound (1.03 M) using anhydrous aluminium chloride (40 g.) The compounds prepared and their properties are listed in Table II.

TABLE II

Aryl from.	Density.	B.P. (15-20mm)	Yield.	Ref.	$[\alpha]_D^{25}$ Indox. (<i>l</i> =1).	Formula.	Found.	Reqd.
Benzene	1.070	106-07°	68.0%	1.4634	4.930	C ₁₂ H ₁₀ O	C: 81.02% H: 9.22	82.10% 9.47
Toluene	1.083	131-32°	71.3	1.4770	3.999	C ₁₄ H ₂₀ O	C: 82.10 H: 9.60	82.35 9.80
<i>m</i> -Xylene	1.003	140-51°	70.0	1.4863	3.555	C ₁₂ H ₁₂ O	C: 82.16 H: 9.82	82.56 10.09
<i>p</i> -Cymene	1.074	168-70°	60.2	1.4031	3.310	C ₁₇ H ₂₆ O	C: 82.54 H: 10.32	82.02 10.57
Chlorobenzene	1.097	132-34°	53.0	1.4390	2.228	C ₁₃ H ₁₇ OCl	C: 69.19 H: 7.17	69.49 7.57
Bromobenzene	1.237	99-102°	49.9	1.4590	1.482	C ₁₂ H ₁₇ OBr	C: 57.26 H: 6.15	57.08 6.31
Ethylbenzene	1.085	101-03°	64.0	1.5010	4.300	C ₁₂ H ₂₂ O	C: 82.17 H: 10.82	82.56 10.09
Anisole	1.580	208-209°	59.4	1.5157	4.048	C ₁₄ H ₂₂ O ₂	C: 76.17 H: 8.90	76.37 9.09
Phenetole	1.143	221-23°	57.3	1.5131	4.666	C ₁₅ H ₂₂ O ₂	C: 76.24 H: 9.10	76.03 9.40

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